

DETERMINATION OF ACETYLCHOLINESTERASE (AChE) ENZYME ACTIVITY IN LOCAL INSECTS

Sh.H. Ibragimova¹, F.Z. Burkhev², H.H. Kushiev³

Gulistan State University, Research Institute of Agrobiotechnology and Biochemistry^{1,2,3}

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Abstract. This article examines the activity and kinetics of the enzyme acetylcholinesterase (AChE), which catalyzes the hydrolysis of acetylcholine (ACh), using the example of Moroccan and Vokhinsk locusts (*Gampsocleis buergeri*). Enzyme activity was determined using the Ellman method. High-quality reagents (Sigma Aldrich), such as phosphate buffer solution, ACh substrate, and Ellman reagent, were used in the experiments. Optical density was determined using a spectrophotometric method. Based on the data obtained, the kinetics of acetylcholinesterase enzyme activity in insects was studied. It was found that the Michaelis-Menten constant (K_m) and the maximum reaction rate (V_{max}) for the Vokhinsk locust are $K_m = 6.05 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $V_{max} = 5.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$, while for Moroccan locusts these values are $K_m = 1.06 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $V_{max} = 7.84 \cdot 10^{-6}$, which was determined by constructing a Lineweaver-Burk plot. A comparative analysis showed that the metabolic rate of the Vakh locust is more intense than that of the Moroccan locust, which is confirmed by the reaction rate values and the Michaelis-Menten constant.

Keywords: acetylcholinesterase (AChE), acetylcholine (ACh), substrate, Ellman method, *Gampsocleis buergeri*, Michaelis–Menten.

Introduction

Enzyme activity in insects does not remain constant throughout their life cycle; at certain stages of development, enzyme activity increases [1-4]. The study of changes in the activity of detoxification enzymes during ontogenesis is important because they determine the ability of insects to develop metabolic resistance to external stress factors, as well as their ability to adapt to the effects of insecticides and acaricides at various stages of development. It has been established that the activity of the enzyme acetylcholinesterase in the housefly varies depending on the stage of development, age, sex, and maturity of the insect. Thus, AChE and ALP (phosphatase enzymes) were studied at the egg, larva, pupa, and imago stages, while in adults, the activity of these enzymes was also analyzed taking into account sexual differences [5].

High alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity is characteristic of tissues with active membrane transport, such as intestinal epithelium; the enzyme plays an important role in assessing the processes of absorption, digestion, and transport of nutrients in the intestine. It has been shown that alkaline phosphatase enzymes in insects are involved in biological processes such as embryogenesis, maturation and degradation of the adult organism, metamorphosis in larval tissues, modulation of hemolymph protein phosphorylation, and mobilization of reserves stored during metamorphosis to meet energy needs [6]. In general, according to the literature, the biological functions of alkaline and acid phosphatases in insects are mainly related to nutrition and development. At the same time, there is evidence of changes in phosphatase activity in insect lines that are resistant to insecticides [7-9].

Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) regulates the transmission of nerve impulses in cholinergic synapses of the nervous system and neuromuscular junctions through the hydrolysis of the

neurotransmitter acetylcholine (ACh) [10]. In invertebrates, one of the non-classical functions of AChE is the detoxification of xenobiotics [11]. Many researchers have noted an increase in the activity of non-specific esterases and AChE in insects that are resistant to insecticides [9,12-15].

Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) plays a crucial role in terminating nerve impulse transmission in the cholinergic nervous system of most animals by hydrolyzing the neurotransmitter acetylcholine (ACh) [16]. In addition, AChE is reported to be widely distributed in various non-neuronal tissues in vertebrates [17,18]. Unlike vertebrates, which have two types of cholinesterases—AChE and butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE) [19,20]—most invertebrates, such as arthropods and nematodes, have only AChE [21,22].

Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) belongs to the family of serine hydrolases, which contain an α/β -hydrolase framework as a common structural element [23]. The catalytically active site of AChE is the precise arrangement of functional groups that form the catalytic center. The biological significance of AChE-catalyzed hydrolysis lies in the rapid termination of the nerve impulse that occurs when acetylcholine (ACh) is released into the synaptic cleft. AChE hydrolyzes ACh to acetic acid and choline in an extremely rapid cycle [24].

Although the primary role of AChE is the hydrolysis of ACh, alternative functions of this enzyme, independent of its catalytic activity, have been identified and extensively studied in neuronal and hematopoietic cells [25]. AChE is involved in various cellular processes in different types of neurons, including non-cholinergic ones, such as cellular activity, proliferation, and neurite growth [26–28].

The complex organization and diverse functions of AChE in different cell types suggest that there may be no general correlation between catalytic activity and AChE protein expression levels. The localization of AChE within a cell may determine its catalytic activity. The influence of intracellular localization of enzymes on their functions is a well-studied process in cell biology and is associated with signaling and transcriptional factors [29-30]. Thus, the intracellular organization of AChE may have a significant impact on its catalytic activity.

Catalytic activity was compared between a panel of primary and immortalized cells, as well as between neuronal and non-neuronal cells. However, no clear correlation was observed between specific AChE catalytic activity and protein expression levels. As shown in the study by Matthew D. Tallberry and co-authors, all cell types expressed the same amount of protein, but catalytic activity varied significantly. Immunofluorescence analysis and confocal microscopy showed that the localization of AChE in the cell differs between neuronal and non-neuronal cells [31].

The Michaelis–Menten model is used to calculate the kinetic characteristics of individual enzymes. According to this model, the enzyme (E) binds to the substrate (S) to form an enzyme–substrate complex (ES), which can either dissociate back into E and S or convert into a product (P):

The rate of product formation (V_0) is determined by the Michaelis-Menten equation; $V_0 = V_{\max} \frac{[S]}{[S] + K_m}$ where V_{\max} is the reaction rate at complete enzyme saturation with the substrate, and K_m is the Michaelis constant. The maximum rate (V_{\max}) is equal to the product of k_2 or k_{kat} and the total enzyme concentration. To determine V_{\max} , the Michaelis-Menten equation is converted to a linear form. If we plot the dependence of $1/V_0$ on $1/[S]$, we get a straight line called the Lineweaver–Burk plot or double reciprocal plot. This line intersects the coordinate

axes: the point of intersection with the ordinate axis (Y) corresponds to $1/V_{\max}$, and the point of intersection with the abscissa axis (X) is equal to $-1/K_m$ [32].

Experimental part

The activity of cholinesterase enzymes, which are among the most important neurohormones in the body, is determined by the amount of choline substrates they hydrolyze and the rate of hydrolysis using the Ellman method [33].

In the Ellman method, the choline molecule formed during substrate hydrolysis (ACh) is determined using Ellman's reagent - 5,5-dithiobis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid). In a phosphate buffer solution with pH = 7.4 (**P3563-10PAK Phosphate Buffered Saline with 0.05% TWEEN20, pH = 7.4, Sigma Aldrich**), the substrate acetylcholine (**A5626-5G Acetylthiocholine iodide > 99%, Sigma Aldrich**) is hydrolyzed by the enzyme. The resulting choline reacts with Ellman's reagent (**D8130 5,5-Dithiobis (2-nitrobenzoic acid) > 98%, Sigma Aldrich**) to form yellow-colored monothionitrobenzoic acid. The amount of monothionitrobenzoic acid formed corresponds to the amount of free SH groups in choline. The hydrolysis rate was determined spectrophotometrically by the intensity of the color at a wavelength of 412 nm.

Main solutions:

1. Phosphate buffer solution with pH = 7.4;
2. Ellman's reagent solution with a concentration of $2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ M (prepared in phosphate buffer with pH = 7.4);
3. Acetylcholine (ACh) substrate solution with a concentration of $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ M, prepared with distilled water.

The mechanism of action of insecticides is directly related to the activity of the AChE enzyme, which manifests itself differently in different insects. In order to determine this activity, two species widely distributed in the Syr Darya region were selected: **The Vakh locust and the Moroccan locust**. The insects were stored frozen (-20°C), after which their heads were removed and homogenized in a phosphate buffer. The homogenized mixture was centrifuged at 0°C in a high-speed refrigerated centrifuge (**High-speed Refrigerated Micro Centrifuge – Dlab D1524R, China**) for 10 minutes at a speed of 10000 rpm, resulting in a precipitate and supernatant. To determine the enzymatic activity, the necessary amounts of solutions and reagents (Table 1) were used, bringing the total volume of the reaction mixture to 4 ml. The experiment used a phosphate buffer with a pH of 7.4, homogenate obtained from insect tissues, as well as the supernatant isolated from it, Ellman's reagent solution, and substrate solution. The mixture was incubated in a water bath at 30°C for 20 minutes.

The enzymatic reaction proceeded after the addition of Ellman's reagent, resulting in the formation of a yellow color, the intensity of which determined the reaction product. The optical density was measured using a spectrophotometer (**HACH DR3900 Vis Spectrophotometer, Germany**) at a wavelength of 412 nm at short intervals (Table 2). As a result of the hydrolysis of substrates in the presence of the enzyme, the optical density gradually increased over time. In addition, when different volumes of substrate (0.08 ml, 0.1 ml, 1 ml, and 2 ml) were added to the same amount of AChE (0.5 ml), a comparative assessment of the activity of the enzyme isolated from the insects under study was performed.

In the next stage, their activity was studied to investigate enzyme kinetics (K_m parameter). To do this, equal amounts of homogenate (0.5 ml) containing the enzyme obtained from insects and various volumes of substrate (0.08 ml, 0.1 ml, 1 ml, and 2 ml) were added to separate test tubes containing a reaction mixture with a total volume of 4 ml. Then, 0.5 ml of Ellman's reagent

was added to each test tube, after which the mixture was brought to phosphate buffer and thoroughly mixed. Incubation was carried out for 20 minutes at a temperature of 30°C in a water bath. At the end of the experiment, the optical density of the solutions was measured at a wavelength of 412 nm.

RESULTS AND THEIR ANALYSIS

The overall hydrolysis of substrates was studied based on the results of their spontaneous and enzymatic hydrolysis using extracts isolated from the heads of insects. For this purpose, spontaneous hydrolysis was determined separately in the presence of phosphate buffer (Table 1; Fig. 1).

Table 1.

Substrate hydrolysis rates over time under the action of acetylcholinesterase enzyme in a homogenate prepared from the head of a locust

Time, min	5 min	10 min	15 min	20 min
Total hydrolysis	0,837	1,393	1,834	2,023
Enzymatic hydrolysis	0,828	1,361	1,765	1,919
Spontaneous hydrolysis	0,009	0,032	0,069	0,104

Figure 1. Total(blue), enzymatic(red), and spontaneous(green) hydrolysis of ACh in a homogenate prepared from the head of Moroccan locusts.

Spontaneous hydrolysis is the spontaneous breakdown of a substrate in solution, with the sum of enzymatic and spontaneous hydrolysis corresponding to the total hydrolysis result.

Table 2.

Dependence of AChE enzyme activity in insects on the concentration of the substrate ACh

Insect species	C(ACh)			
	0,08	0,1	1	2
Moroccan	0,434	0,596	1,641	2,676
Vakh locust	0,47	0,576	1,272	2,023

Fig. 2. Graph showing the dependence of AChE enzyme activity in Moroccan(blue) and Vakh(red) locusts on ACh concentration

To determine the rate of substrate hydrolysis in the presence of the enzyme, acetylcholine base was used in various concentrations (Table 3), after which the enzyme kinetics were studied using the Lineweaver-Burk method.

The following formula was used to process the obtained data:

$A = E \cdot C \cdot I$ where $E = 17500$. Based on the calculation of the concentration of the substrate that entered into the reaction, the average reaction rate (v) was determined. The reaction rate was calculated as the ratio of the change in concentration (ΔC) to the time interval (Δt) (Table 4): $v = \Delta C / \Delta t$.

Kinetics of hydrolysis of substrate ACh at various concentrations in a homogenate prepared from the head section of Moroccan and Vakh locusts (Gampsocleis buergeri)

$C_{(ACh)}$	Moroccan locust		Vakh locust	
	Concentration, [C] (mol)	Velocity, V (mol/l•min)	Concentration, [C] (mol)	Velocity, V (mol/l•min)
0,08	$2 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1,343 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1,24 \cdot 10^{-6}$
0,1	$2,5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1,646 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2,5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1,703 \cdot 10^{-6}$
1	$2,5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3,731 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2,5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4,689 \cdot 10^{-6}$
2	$5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5,78 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$7,646 \cdot 10^{-6}$

Specific concentrations and reaction rates were plotted on the Lineweaver–Burk graph, based on which the Michaelis–Menten constant (K_m) characterizing the activity of the acetylcholinesterase enzyme was calculated for Moroccan and Wahai locusts.

Fig. 3. Determination of the Michaelis–Menten constant using the Lineweaver–Burk plot

a) Moroccan locust – $K_m = 6.05 \cdot 10^{-5}$ $V_{max} = 5.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$

b) Vakh locust – $K_m = 1.06 \cdot 10^{-4}$ $V_{max} = 7.84 \cdot 10^{-6}$

Using the Lineweaver–Burk method, the maximum reaction rate (V_{max}) and Michaelis–Menten constant (K_m) characterizing enzyme activity were determined. Given the inverse relationship between K_m and enzymatic activity, it was found that acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity is higher in Vakh locusts than in Moroccan locusts. This indicates that the high activity of neuroenzymatic processes in the Vakh locust ensures its resistance to external stress factors.

CONCLUSION

Determining the activity of neurohormones in insects is one of the key factors in pest control. In this study, the activity of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) in Moroccan and Vakh locusts, which are widespread in the Syr Darya region, was studied using the Ellman method. Based on spectrophotometric measurements, the kinetics of enzyme activity in the studied objects were analyzed using the Lineweaver–Burk graphical method. The Michaelis–Menten constant (K_m), reflecting enzymatic activity, was determined using this method. The study found that the K_m constant and reaction rate (V_{max}) characterizing AChE activity were as follows for the Vakh locust: $K_m = 6.05 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $V_{max} = 5.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$, while for Moroccan locusts, these values were $K_m = 1.06 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $V_{max} = 7.84 \cdot 10^{-6}$. The results confirm that the higher AChE activity in the Wahai locust provides it with increased resistance to various external stress factors.

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